

“WIND” SO‘ZI ISHTIROK ETGAN FBLARDA FE‘LLI KOMPONENTNI ALMASHTIRISH

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada ingliz tilidagi “wind” sozi ishtirok etgan FBning komponentlarini almashtirishning o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit sozlar: frazeologik birlik, okkazional, komponent, ekspressiv.

Frazeologik birliklar (FB)ning okkazional qayta o‘zgartirishning boshqa usuli FBning komponentlarini almashtirish hisoblanadi.

Ushbu stilistik usulni qarab chiqishning maqsadi FBlardagi leksik-semantik guruh (LSG)ning a‘zolari almashtirishga moyilmi yoki ular bu holda o‘zlarining konstantligini saqlab qoladilarmi, shuni kuzatishdan iborat.

Qo‘yilgan vazifani hal qilishga erishish uchun tadqiqotning materialida qayd qilingan almashtirishlarning barcha turlarini ko‘rib chiqish zarur.

Faktik materialning tahlili FBning fe‘lli komponentini almashtirishning bir qator hollarini aniqladi. Almashtirish natijasida okkazional jihatdan qayta o‘zgartirilgan FBlar boshlang‘ich FBlar bilan turli xil semantik munosabatlarga kirishadi. Bu munosabatlar sinonimik, antonimik xarakterga ega bo‘lishlari mumkin; almashtirilayotgan komponentlar mutlaqo qandaydir munosabatlar bilan bog‘liq bo‘lmasliklari mumkin.

Fe‘lli komponentni almashtirishning qayd qilingan barcha hollari sinonimik xarakterga ega. Keyingi misollarni qarab chiqamiz.

Almashtiriladigan fe‘lli komponentlarning turli tumanligini “to sail close to (near) the wind” FBgida hamda “to sail before (with) the wind” FBda kuzatamiz.

1. *There are four of them, sir, and all are coming down before the wind, wing and wing, carrying their lugs reefed.* (J.F.Cooper. Short Stories. – P. 261)
2. *Then they (boats) ran before the wind for Cayo Cruz.* (E.Hemingway. Islands in the Stream. – P. 354)
3. *... and then gradually became obscured by the passing vapor that was moving before the wind at a vast distance below the clouds themselves.* (J.F.Cooper. The Spy. – P. 347)
4. *The Grymsdikes may have come close to the wind pretty often, but none of them suffered the disgrace of ever getting caught.* (J.F.Cooper. – P. 460)

Ko‘rinib turibdiki, keltirilgan misollarda FBdagi fe‘lli komponentning almashtirilishi aslini olganda yangi hech narsani kiritmaydi, chunki almashtirish tez-tez qo‘llaniladigan, juda tanish bo‘lib qolgan FBga diqqatni tortish uchun amalga oshiriladi.

Quyida keltirilgan misollarda fe‘lli komponent kam qo‘llaniladigan fe‘llar bilan almashtiriladi. Buning hisobiga FBning yangilanishi sodir bo‘ladi hamda uning ekspressiv ma‘naviy o‘zgachaligi ortadi:

FB “to ride out (yoki weather) the storm”

1. *The horseman did not wait to hear more than the advice to pursue his course up the road, but he had slowly turned his horse towards the bars, and was gathering the folds of an ample cloak around his manly form, preparatory to facing the storm again when something in the speech of the female suddenly arrested the movement.* (J.F.Cooper. The Spy. – P. 28)

2. *On abuse, on reproach, on calumny, it is easy to smile, but painful, indeed, is the panegyric of those we contemn. Often had Moore gazed with a brilliant countenance over howling crowds from a hostile husting: he had crested the storm of unpopularity with gallant bearing and soul elate.* (Ch.Bronte. Shirley. – P. 527)

Faraz qilish mumkin ediki, variantlarga ega bo'lgan FBlar almashtirishga kamroq tortilganlar, chunki muallifda odat doirasida ham fe'lli komponentni tanlash bor, ammo tadqiqot materiali ko'rsatadiki, okkazional qayta o'zgartirishlarga variantlarga ega bo'lgan FBlar ham tortiladilar.

FB “to cast (fling, throw) caution (prudence) to the winds”

No! she didn't blame Denis. She felt, instead, tint she must fly to him. Caution was now abandoned to the winds in the extremity of her anguish and, with a strained face, she walked along Main Street, at the far end of which stood the Loniond Wine and Sprit Vaults. (A.Christie. Peril at End house. – P. 127)

Fe'lli komponentning sinonimik almashtirishiga yana bitta misol keltiramiz:

FB “to sow the wind and reap the whirlwind”

Folks that plant the wind reap the whirlwind. (O.Davis. Icebound. act III)

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